

EXPLICIT ESTIMATES FOR INCOMPLETE EXPONENTIAL SUMS

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Abstract

We obtain explicit estimates for the incomplete exponential sum

$$S_p(f, B) := \sum_{x=1}^B e_p(f(x)),$$

where $e_p(u) = e^{2\pi i u/p}$, $f(x)$ is a polynomial over $\mathbb{Z}/(p)$, and $1 \leq B \leq p$, such as the following. For any f of degree at least 2,

$$|S_p(f, B)| \leq \min\left\{\frac{2}{\pi^2} \log p + 3.29 + \frac{B}{p}, \frac{4}{\pi^2} \log p + \frac{B}{p} + .35\right\} \Phi,$$

where $\Phi = \max_{0 \leq y \leq p-1} \left| \sum_{x=1}^p e_p(f(x) + yx) \right|$. For any quadratic polynomial f and B with $\sqrt{p} < B < p/2$, we have $|S_p(f, B)| < \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi} p \log(16.6B^2/p)}$. For any monic cubic polynomial, and B with $4p^{1/3} < B < \sqrt{p/12}$, we have $|S_p(f, B)| < (Bp)^{1/4} \sqrt{\log p}$.

1. Introduction

Let p be a prime, $\mathbb{Z}_p = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ denote the finite field $\mathbb{Z}/(p)$, and $e_p(\cdot) := e^{2\pi i \cdot/p}$. For any polynomial $f(x)$ over \mathbb{Z} or \mathbb{Z}_p , and positive integer B with $1 \leq B \leq p$, let $S_p(f, B)$ denote the *incomplete* exponential sum

$$S_p(f, B) := \sum_{x=1}^B e_p(f(x)),$$

and put $S_p(f) := S_p(f, p)$ for the *complete* sum. Let $d_p = d_p(f)$ denote the degree of f viewed as a polynomial over \mathbb{Z}_p . Define

$$\Phi = \Phi(f, p) := \max_{0 \leq y \leq p-1} \left| \sum_{x=1}^p e_p(f(x) + yx) \right|. \quad (1.1)$$

A standard estimate for $S_p(f, B)$, dating back to the work of Davenport and Heilbronn [5, 6], is the bound

$$|S_p(f, B)| \ll \Phi \log p. \quad (1.2)$$

Thus by the Weil bound [28], $\Phi \leq (d_p - 1)\sqrt{p}$, we have $|S_p(f, B)| \ll d_p \sqrt{p} \log p$ for $d_p \geq 2$. The first objective of this paper is to make (1.2) explicit.

Theorem 1.1. *For any prime p , polynomial f over \mathbb{Z} or \mathbb{Z}_p with $d_p(f) \geq 2$, and integer B with $1 \leq B \leq p$, we have*

$$|S_p(f, B)| \leq \min\left\{ \frac{2}{\pi^2} \log p + 3.29 + \frac{B}{p}, \frac{4}{\pi^2} \log p + \frac{B}{p} + .35 \right\} \Phi. \quad (1.3)$$

The second expression in (1.3) is less than the first for $p < 1.99 \cdot 10^6$, and implies the following clean bound, first established by Vinogradov [27] for $p > 60$.

Corollary 1.1. *For any prime $p \geq 5$, polynomial f over \mathbb{Z} or \mathbb{Z}_p with $d_p(f) \geq 2$, and integer B with $1 \leq B \leq p$, we have*

$$|S_p(f, B)| < \Phi \log p. \quad (1.4)$$

The estimate in Theorem 1.1 is trivial for $B < \frac{2}{\pi^2}(d_p - 1)\sqrt{p} \log p$ if we employ the Weil bound for Φ . The second objective of this paper is to obtain an explicit nontrivial bound on $S_p(f, B)$ for B in this range using the method of Weyl. We restrict our attention here to second and third degree polynomials.

1.1. Quadratic Polynomials

Korolev [14], improving on earlier works of Hardy and Littlewood [8], Fielder, Jurkat and Köner [7], and Oskolkov [21], established that for $p \nmid a$, and $1 \leq B \leq p$, one has $|S_p(ax^2, B)| \leq 3.5254 \sqrt{p} + 1$. For a general quadratic $f(x) = ax^2 + bx$ with $p \nmid a$, by completing the square and expressing $S_p(f(x), B)$ as a sum or difference of two monomial quadratic sums, one deduces from the Korolev bound that

$$|S_p(ax^2 + bx, B)| \leq 7.0508 \sqrt{p} + 2, \quad (1.5)$$

for $1 \leq B \leq p$. The bound is nontrivial for $B > 7.06 \sqrt{p}$, and yields the bound $|S_p(ax^2 + bx, B)| < B/2$ for $B > 14.11 \sqrt{p}$. Lehmer [16] studied in detail the case where $a = 1$, obtaining for $1 \leq B \leq p$,

$$|S_p(x^2, B)| \leq \begin{cases} \sqrt{p} + O(1), & \text{if } p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}; \\ 1.0625461 \sqrt{p} + O(1), & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}. \end{cases} \quad (1.6)$$

Moreover, the constants on the \sqrt{p} in (1.6) are sharp. We prove the following.

Theorem 1.2. *For any quadratic polynomial $f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c$ with $p \nmid a$, and positive integer B with $\sqrt{p} < B < p/2$, we have*

$$|S_p(f, B)| < \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi} p \log(16.6B^2/p)}. \quad (1.7)$$

This improves on Theorem 1.1 for all p , and improves on (1.5) for all p, B with $B < 2.22 \cdot 10^{16} \sqrt{p}$. The bound in (1.7) is nontrivial for $B > 1.53\sqrt{p}$. We derive from (1.7), for instance, that if $B > 3.73\sqrt{p}$, then $|S_p(f, B)| < B/2$. Such a bound is not possible for B slightly smaller than \sqrt{p} ; see Example 6.1. For $B > p/2$, see Corollary 6.1.

1.2. Cubic Polynomials

We are not aware of any explicit Weyl type estimates for cubic polynomials, but see [9] for related work. Here we establish the following. Put

$$\delta_p := \frac{1.0661}{\log \log p}.$$

Theorem 1.3. *For any cubic polynomial $f(x) = ax^3 + bx^2 + cx$ with $p \nmid a$, and positive integer B , we have*

$$|S_p(f, B)| \leq \begin{cases} 1.1 B^{\frac{1}{4}} p^{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{\delta_p}{4}} \log^{\frac{1}{4}} p, & \text{for } 1 \leq B < \sqrt{p/2}; \\ 1.38(1 + \frac{p}{B^2})^{\frac{1}{4}} B^{\frac{3}{4}} p^{\frac{\delta_p}{2}} \log^{\frac{1}{4}} p, & \text{for } \sqrt{p/2} < B \leq p. \end{cases}$$

The estimate is nontrivial for $B > 1.14 p^{\frac{1}{3} + \frac{\delta_p}{3}} \log^{\frac{1}{3}} p$ and improves on Theorem 1.1 for $B \ll_{\varepsilon} p^{\frac{2}{3} - \varepsilon}$.

For monic cubics we can eliminate the term $p^{\delta_p/4}$ for small B .

Theorem 1.4. *For any cubic polynomial $f(x) = x^3 + bx^2 + cx$ and positive integer B with $4p^{\frac{1}{3}} < B < \sqrt{p/12}$, we have*

$$|S_p(f, B)| < (Bp)^{\frac{1}{4}} \log^{\frac{1}{4}}(B^3/p) \log^{\frac{1}{4}}(Bp).$$

In particular, $|S_p(f, B)| < (Bp)^{\frac{1}{4}} \log^{\frac{1}{2}} p$ for $B < \sqrt{p/12}$. The theorem yields a nontrivial bound for $|S_p(f, B)|$ for $p > 5 \cdot 10^8$, $B > p^{\frac{1}{3}} (\log^{\frac{1}{3}} p) \log \log p$, and improves on Theorem 1.1 whenever it applies. The theorem also yields bounds of the following type for sufficiently large p : For $B > 2p^{\frac{1}{3}} (\log^{\frac{1}{3}} p) \log \log p$, we have $|S_p(f, B)| < B/2$.

2. Proof of Theorem 1.1, Part I

To obtain the second bound in (1.3) we use the *method of completing a sum*, a method dates back at least to the 1918 work of Polya [23], Vinogradov [26], Landau

[15] and Schur [24], who used it for estimating the multiplicative character sum $\sum_{x=1}^B \chi(x)$, yielding the well known Polya-Vinogradov inequality. For the sum at hand, the first appearance we know of is the 1936 work of Davenport and Heilbronn [5, 6], who treated the case of monomials, followed by Hua [10] who treated general $f(x)$. Let $T_p(B)$ denote the trigonometric sum

$$T_p(B) := \frac{1}{p} \sum_{y=1}^{p-1} \left| \frac{\sin(\pi B y/p)}{\sin(\pi y/p)} \right|.$$

Lemma 2.1. *For any prime p , polynomial $f(x)$ over \mathbb{Z} or \mathbb{Z}_p , and positive integer B with $1 \leq B \leq p$, we have*

$$S_p(f, B) = \frac{B}{p} \sum_{x=1}^p e_p(f(x)) + \theta T_p(B) \max_{1 \leq y \leq p-1} \left| \sum_{x=1}^p e_p(f(x) + yx) \right|, \quad (2.1)$$

for some θ with $|\theta| \leq 1$,

Proof. Let $I = \{1, 2, \dots, B\} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}_p$, and 1_I be the characteristic function of I with Fourier expansion

$$1_I(x) = \sum_{y=0}^{p-1} a(y) e_p(yx),$$

where $a(0) = B/p$, and for $1 \leq y \leq p-1$,

$$a(y) = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{x=1}^B e_p(-yx) = \frac{1}{p} e_p\left(\frac{-B-1}{2} y\right) \frac{\sin(\pi B y/p)}{\sin(\pi y/p)}.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{x=1}^B e_p(f(x)) &= \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} 1_I(x) e_p(f(x)) = \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} \sum_{y=0}^{p-1} a(y) e_p(yx) e_p(f(x)) \\ &= a(0) \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} e_p(f(x)) + \sum_{y=1}^{p-1} a(y) \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} e_p(f(x) + yx), \end{aligned}$$

and so

$$\left| \sum_{x=1}^B e_p(f(x)) - \frac{B}{p} \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} e_p(f(x)) \right| \leq \Phi' \sum_{y=1}^{p-1} |a(y)| = \Phi' T_p(B),$$

where $\Phi' := \max_{1 \leq y \leq p-1} \left| \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} e_p(f(x) + yx) \right|$. \square

It is elementary to show $T_p(B) < \log p$; see, e.g., [11, Theorem 7.3]. Improvements were made by Vinogradov [27], Lidl and Neiderreiter [17], Cochrane [3],

Kongting [13], Peral [22], and Cochrane and Peral [4]. Presently, the best bound is that of Bourgain, Cochrane, Paulhus and Pinner [2, Lemma 11.1], a slight improvement on [3, Theorem 1]: For any prime $p \geq 5$ and $1 \leq B \leq p$,

$$T_p(B) \leq \frac{4}{\pi^2} \log p + .35. \quad (2.2)$$

The constant $4/\pi^2$ on the $\log p$ term is best possible.

Let $\Phi = \Phi(f, p)$ be as defined in (1.1).

Lemma 2.2. *For any prime p , and polynomial f over \mathbb{Z} , we have*

$$\Phi(f, p) \geq \sqrt{p}.$$

Proof. This is immediate from the identity

$$\sum_{y=0}^{p-1} \left| \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} e_p(f(x) + yx) \right|^2 = \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} \sum_{v=0}^{p-1} e_p(f(u) - f(v)) \sum_{y=0}^{p-1} e_p(y(u - v)) = p^2.$$

□

Proof of Theorem 1.1, Part I. From (2.2) and (2.1) we get for $p \geq 5$,

$$|S_p(f, B)| \leq \frac{B}{p} \Phi + |T_p(B)| \Phi \leq \frac{B}{p} \Phi + \left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} \log p + .35 \right) \Phi,$$

yielding the second bound in (1.3). For $p = 2, 3$, we note that using $|S_p(f, B)| \leq B$ and the bound $\Phi \geq \sqrt{p}$ from Lemma 2.2, it suffices to show that

$$B \leq \left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} \log p + \frac{B}{p} + .35 \right) \sqrt{p},$$

that is,

$$B \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{p}} \right) \leq \left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} \log p + .35 \right) \sqrt{p}.$$

Computation confirms this for $p = 2, 3$, and $B \leq p$. □

To prove the first bound in (1.3), we need a number of lemmas on trigonometric sums.

3. Lemmas on Trigonometric Sums

Lemma 3.1. ([3, Lemma 2.2]). *For $0 < x < 1$, we have*

$$\frac{1}{\sin \pi x} < \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\frac{1}{x} + \frac{2x}{1 - x^2} \right).$$

Lemma 3.2. *If p is a prime, $1 \leq B < p/2$, and $p \nmid a$, we have*

$$\sum_{h=1}^B \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi ah/p)|} < \frac{p}{\pi} \left(\log B + \gamma + \frac{1}{2B} \right) + \frac{pB(B+1)}{\pi(p^2 - B^2)}.$$

Proof. We first show that the maximum value of the sum occurs when $a = 1$. Since $B < p/2$, we have $0 < \sin(\pi/p) < \sin(2\pi/p) < \dots < \sin(B\pi/p)$. If there is a value of a where the sum exceeds $\sum_{h=1}^B \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi h/p)|}$, then there must exist an integer b and distinct values h, h' with $1 \leq h, h' \leq B$, such that $ah \equiv \pm b \pmod{p}$ and $ah' \equiv \pm b \pmod{p}$. Then either $ah \equiv ah' \pmod{p}$, or $ah \equiv -ah' \pmod{p}$. In the first case we have $h = h'$, a contradiction. In the second case, $p \mid a(h + h')$. Since $2 \leq h + h' \leq 2B < p$, we again have a contradiction. Thus, the maximum value is attained when $a = \pm 1$.

By Lemma 3.1 and the Euler-Maclaurin estimate $\sum_{1 \leq n \leq x} \frac{1}{n} < \log x + \gamma + \frac{1}{2x}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{h=1}^B \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi h/p)|} &< \frac{p}{\pi} \sum_{h=1}^B \left(\frac{1}{h} + \frac{2h}{p^2 - h^2} \right) \\ &< \frac{p}{\pi} \left(\log B + \gamma + \frac{1}{2B} \right) + \frac{2p}{\pi(p^2 - B^2)} \sum_{h=1}^B h \\ &= \frac{p}{\pi} \left(\log B + \gamma + \frac{1}{2B} \right) + \frac{pB(B+1)}{\pi(p^2 - B^2)}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 3.3. *If p is a prime and $\sqrt{p/\pi} < B < p/2$, then for any a with $p \nmid a$, we have*

$$\sum_{h=1}^B \min \left\{ B, \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi ah/p)|} \right\} < \frac{p}{\pi} \left(\log(\pi B^2/p) + 1 + \frac{\pi B}{p} \right) + \frac{pB(B+1)}{\pi(p^2 - B^2)}.$$

Proof. As in the preceding proof, we may assume that $a = 1$. By Lemma 3.1, the estimate $\sum_{u < h \leq v} \frac{1}{h} < \log(v/u) + \frac{1}{u}$ for real u, v with $v \geq u \geq 1$, and noting that $p/(\pi B) < B$ by assumption, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{h=1}^B \min \left\{ B, \frac{1}{|\sin(\pi h/p)|} \right\} &\leq \sum_{1 \leq h \leq p/(\pi B)} B + \sum_{p/(\pi B) < h \leq B} \frac{p}{\pi} \left(\frac{1}{h} + \frac{2h}{p^2 - h^2} \right) \\ &\leq \frac{p}{\pi} + \frac{p}{\pi} \sum_{p/(\pi B) < h \leq B} \frac{1}{h} + \frac{2p}{\pi(p^2 - B^2)} \sum_{h=1}^B h \\ &\leq \frac{p}{\pi} + \frac{p}{\pi} \left(\log(\pi B^2/p) + \frac{\pi B}{p} \right) + \frac{pB(B+1)}{\pi(p^2 - B^2)}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 3.4. ([3, Lemma 2.1]). *For any positive integer K and real number ξ ,*

$$\sum_{y=1}^K \frac{|\sin(y\xi)|}{y} < \frac{2}{\pi} \left(\log(K+1) + \gamma + \log 2 \right) + \frac{3}{\pi(K+1)}.$$

In particular, since $\log(K+1) < \log K + \frac{1}{K}$,

$$\sum_{y=1}^K \frac{|\sin(y\xi)|}{y} < \frac{2}{\pi} \log K + \frac{2}{\pi}(\gamma + \log 2) + \frac{5}{\pi K}. \quad (3.1)$$

Lemma 3.5. *For any positive integers q, K, B , with $K < q$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{|\sin(\pi Bk/q)|}{|\sin(\pi k/q)|} < \frac{2}{\pi^2} q \log K + \frac{2q}{\pi^2}(\gamma + \log 2) + \frac{q}{\pi} \frac{K}{q-K} + \frac{5q}{\pi^2 K}.$$

Proof. By Lemma 3.1, and then (3.1),

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{|\sin(\pi Bk/q)|}{|\sin(\pi k/q)|} &< \frac{q}{\pi} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{|\sin(\pi Bk/q)|}{k} + \frac{q}{\pi} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{|\sin \pi Bk/q|}{q-k} \\ &\leq \frac{q}{\pi} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \log K + \frac{2}{\pi}(\gamma + \log 2) + \frac{5}{\pi K} \right) + \frac{q}{\pi} \frac{K}{q-K}. \end{aligned}$$

□

4. Proof of Theorem 1.1, Part II

We make use of the Beurling–Selberg majorizing and minorizing functions. The following comes from the work of Vaaler [25, Theorem 19], but is stated here in the form appearing in [19].

Lemma 4.1. *For any interval $J = [a, b]$ in \mathbb{T} with length $b - a < 1$, and for any positive integer K , there are trigonometric polynomials*

$$S_{\pm}(x) = \sum_{k=-K}^K \alpha_{\pm}(k) e^{2\pi i k x},$$

such that $\alpha_{\pm}(0) = b - a \pm \frac{1}{K+1}$ and

$$S_-(x) \leq 1_J(x) \leq S_+(x), \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{T}.$$

Let $I = \{1, 2, \dots, B\} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}_p$. We apply Lemma 4.1 with $J = [\frac{1}{2p}, \frac{B}{p} + \frac{1}{2p}]$, so that, $1_J(\frac{n}{p}) = 1_I(n)$ for $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, and $\alpha_{\pm}(0) = \frac{B}{p} \pm \frac{1}{K+1}$. Set

$$T_{\pm}(x) := S_{\pm}\left(\frac{x}{p}\right) = \sum_{k=-K}^K \alpha_{\pm}(k) e_p(kx). \quad (4.1)$$

If $K < \frac{p}{2}$, then we can view T_{\pm} as functions on \mathbb{Z}_p with Fourier expansions as given in (4.1). Let $1_I(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} a(k)e_p(kx)$ be the Fourier expansion for $1_I(x)$. Then for $|k| \leq K$,

$$\alpha_{\pm}(k) = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} T_{\pm}(x)e_p(-kx), \quad a(k) = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} 1_I(x)e_p(-kx).$$

Also, by design, for any $x \in \mathbb{Z}_p$,

$$T_-(x) \leq 1_I(x) \leq T_+(x).$$

Thus for $|k| \leq K$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |a(k) - \alpha_-(k)| &\leq \frac{1}{p} \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} |1_I(x) - T_-(x)| = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} (1_I(x) - T_-(x)) \\ &= \frac{1}{p} \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} 1_I(x) - \frac{1}{p} \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} T_-(x) = a(0) - \alpha(0) = \frac{1}{K+1}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

and the same for $|a(k) - \alpha_+(k)|$.

Set $T = T_{\pm}$, $\alpha = \alpha_{\pm}$ with a fixed \pm choice. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{x=1}^B e_p(f(x)) &= \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} 1_I(x)e_p(f(x)) = \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} T(x)e_p(f(x)) + \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} (1_I(x) - T(x))e_p(f(x)) \\ &= \Sigma_1 + \Sigma_2, \end{aligned}$$

say. Now, as seen in (4.2), $|\Sigma_2| \leq \frac{p}{K+1}$ and for $|k| \leq K$, we have $|\alpha(k)| \leq |a(k)| + \frac{1}{K+1}$. Using the Fourier expansion for T , we have

$$\Sigma_1 = \sum_{k=-K}^K \alpha(k) \sum_{x=0}^{p-1} e_p(f(x) + kx),$$

and so with Φ denoting a uniform upper bound on the exponential sum over x ,

$$|\Sigma_1| \leq \Phi \sum_{k=-K}^K |\alpha(k)| \leq \Phi \left(|\alpha(0)| + \sum_{1 \leq |k| \leq K} \left(|a(k)| + \frac{1}{K+1} \right) \right).$$

Now $\alpha(0) = \frac{B}{p} \pm \frac{1}{K+1}$ and by Lemma 3.5,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{1 \leq |k| \leq K} |a(k)| &= \frac{2}{p} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{|\sin(\pi k B/p)|}{|\sin(\pi k/p)|} \\ &\leq \frac{4}{\pi^2} \log K + \frac{4}{\pi^2} (\gamma + \log 2) + \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{K}{p-K} + \frac{10}{\pi^2 K}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for $T = T_-$,

$$\begin{aligned} |\Sigma_1| &\leq \Phi\left(\frac{B}{p} - \frac{1}{K+1}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} \log K + \frac{4}{\pi^2}(\gamma + \log 2) + \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{K}{p-K} + \frac{10}{\pi^2 K} + \frac{2K}{K+1}\right) \\ &= \Phi\left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} \log K + C_1 - \frac{3}{K+1} + \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{K}{p-K} + \frac{10}{\pi^2 K}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $C_1 = 2 + \frac{4}{\pi^2}(\gamma + \log 2) + \frac{B}{p} < 2.51486 + \frac{B}{p}$, and

$$|\Sigma_1| + |\Sigma_2| \leq \frac{p}{K+1} + \Phi\left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} \log K + C_1 + \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{K}{p-K} + \frac{10}{\pi^2 K} - \frac{3}{K+1}\right).$$

Let $K := \lfloor \frac{\pi^2}{4} \sqrt{p} \rfloor$. Noting that the coefficient on Φ is increasing with K , we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\Sigma_1| + |\Sigma_2| &\leq \frac{4}{\pi^2} \sqrt{p} + \Phi\left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} \log \frac{\pi^2}{4} \sqrt{p} + C_1 + \frac{2\pi}{4\sqrt{p}-\pi^2} + \frac{40}{\pi^4 \sqrt{p}} - \frac{12}{\pi^2 \sqrt{p}}\right) \\ &\leq \frac{2}{\pi^2} \Phi \log p + \frac{4}{\pi^2} \sqrt{p} + \Phi\left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} \log \frac{\pi^2}{4} + C_1 + \frac{2\pi}{4\sqrt{p}-\pi^2} - \frac{.805}{\sqrt{p}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Using $\sqrt{p} \leq \Phi$ we get

$$|\Sigma_1| + |\Sigma_2| \leq \frac{2}{\pi^2} \Phi \log p + \Phi\left(C_2 + \frac{2\pi}{4\sqrt{p}-\pi^2} - \frac{.805}{\sqrt{p}}\right),$$

with

$$C_2 = \frac{4}{\pi^2} + \frac{4}{\pi^2} \log \frac{\pi^2}{4} + C_1 \leq 3.28619 + \frac{B}{p}.$$

Thus for $p > 43000$ we have

$$|S_p(f, B)| \leq |\Sigma_1| + |\Sigma_2| \leq \frac{2}{\pi^2} \Phi \log p + \Phi(3.29 + \frac{B}{p}).$$

For $p < 43000$, the same holds by the second bound in (1.3), already established.

5. Proof of Corollary 1.1

In this section we establish Corollary 1.1.

Proof of Corollary 1.1. For $p \geq 11$, the corollary follows immediately from Theorem 1.1, that is, $\frac{4}{\pi^2} \log p + 1.35 < \log p$. For $p = 7$, we use Lemma 2.2 to get $\Phi \log p \geq \sqrt{7} \log 7 > 5.148$, and so (1.4) is immediate for $B \leq 5$, that is, $|S_p(f, B)| \leq B < 5.148 < \Phi \log p$. For $B = 7$, the sum is a complete sum, and so the result again is immediate. For $B = 6$, we have

$$|S_p(f, 6)| \leq |S_p(f)| + 1 \leq \Phi + 1 < \Phi \log 7.$$

For $p = 5$ the same argument holds, that is, for $B \leq 3$ or $B = 5$, the result is immediate, while for $B = 4$, we can use $|S_p(f, 4)| \leq \Phi + 1$ to get the result. \square

Remark 5.1. For $p = 3$, inequality (1.4) is immediate for $B = 1$ or 3 , while for $B = 2$, if f is not constant mod 3 on $[1, 2]$, we have $|S_p(f, B)| = |1 + e^{2\pi i/3}| = 1$, yielding the inequality. For $p = 2$, (1.4) is immediate for $B = 1$, while for $B = 2$, if f is not constant mod 2, then $S_p(f, B) = S_p(f) = 0$.

6. Proof of Theorem 1.2

Let γ denote Euler's constant, $\gamma := .577215664\dots$, and

$$R := \frac{2pB(B+1)}{\pi(p^2 - B^2)}.$$

Proposition 6.1. *For any quadratic polynomial $f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c$ with $p \nmid a$, and positive integer B with $\sqrt{p} < B < p/2$, we have*

$$|S_p(f, B)|^2 \leq \min \left\{ \frac{2p}{\pi} \log(B^2/p) + 1.366p + 3B + R, \right. \\ \left. \frac{2p}{\pi} \log B + .368p + B + \frac{p}{\pi B} + R \right\}. \quad (6.1)$$

Proof. Let $f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c$ with $p \nmid a$, and B be an integer with $1 \leq B < p/2$. Following the method of Weyl, letting $y = x + h$, we have

$$|S_p(f, B)|^2 = \sum_{x=1}^B \sum_{y=1}^B e_p(f(y) - f(x)) = B + 2\mathcal{R} \sum_{1 \leq x < y \leq B} e_p(f(y) - f(x)) \\ = B + 2\mathcal{R} \sum_{h=1}^{B-1} \sum_{x=1}^{B-h} e_p(2hax + ah^2 + bh) \leq B + 2 \sum_{h=1}^{B-1} \left| \sum_{x=1}^{B-h} e_p(2hax) \right|, \quad (6.2)$$

and so

$$|S_p(f, B)|^2 \leq B + 2 \sum_{h=1}^{B-1} \min \left\{ B - h, \frac{1}{|\sin(2\pi ha/p)|} \right\}. \quad (6.3)$$

We deduce from Lemma 3.3 that for $\sqrt{p} < B < p/2$, we have

$$|S_p(f, B)|^2 \leq B + \frac{2p}{\pi} \left(\log(\pi B^2/p) + 1 + \frac{\pi B}{p} \right) + R \\ = \frac{2p}{\pi} \log(B^2/p) + \frac{2p}{\pi} \log(\pi e) + 3B + R \\ < \frac{2p}{\pi} \log(B^2/p) + 1.366p + 3B + R.$$

Similarly, by Lemma 3.2,

$$|S_p(f, B)|^2 \leq B + \frac{2p}{\pi} \left(\log B + \gamma + \frac{1}{2B} \right) + R \\ = \frac{2p}{\pi} \log B + \frac{2\gamma}{\pi} p + B + \frac{p}{\pi B} + R \\ < \frac{2p}{\pi} \log B + .368p + B + \frac{p}{\pi B} + R.$$

□

We can now establish Theorem 1.2.

Proof of Theorem 1.2. If $B < 1.52\sqrt{p}$, we have trivially

$$|S_p(f, B)|^2 \leq B^2 < \frac{2p}{\pi} \log(16.6B^2/p),$$

since letting $u := \frac{B^2}{p}$, we have $u \leq \frac{2}{\pi} \log(16.6u)$ for $u < (1.52)^2$. Thus, we may assume that $B \geq 1.52\sqrt{p}$. Using this restriction on B and computer computation, we can readily verify the theorem for $p < 2000$ using (6.3). Suppose now that $p > 2000$. If $B < .136p$ so that $R < .0121p$, we use the first bound in (6.1) to get the result provided that

$$\frac{2p}{\pi} \log(B^2/p) + 1.366p + 3B + .0121p \leq \frac{2p}{\pi} \log(16.6B^2/p),$$

that is,

$$1.3781p + 3B \leq \frac{2p}{\pi} \log(16.6).$$

Since $B < .136p$, the latter holds.

Suppose now that $B = \lambda p$ with $.136 \leq \lambda < .5$. The second bound in (6.1) gives the result provided that

$$\frac{2p}{\pi} \log B + .368p + B + \frac{p}{\pi B} + R < \frac{2p}{\pi} \log(16.6B^2/p),$$

that is,

$$.368 + \lambda + \frac{1}{\pi\lambda p} + \frac{2\lambda}{\pi} \frac{\lambda+1/p}{1-\lambda^2} \leq \frac{2}{\pi} \log(16.6\lambda),$$

which is the case for $p > 2000$ and $\lambda \geq .136$. \square

For intervals of length $1 \leq B \leq p$, we have the following uniform bound.

Corollary 6.1. *For any quadratic polynomial $f(x) = ax^2 + bx + c$ with $p \nmid a$, and positive integer B with $1 \leq B \leq p$, we have*

$$|S_p(f, B)| < \sqrt{p} + \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi} p \log p + \frac{1}{2} p}.$$

This improves on (1.5) for $p < 4.31 \cdot 10^{24}$.

Proof. Inserting $B = \frac{p-1}{2}$ into the second expression in (6.1), we get for $p \geq 31$,

$$|S_p(f, \frac{p-1}{2})|^2 < \frac{2p}{\pi} \log \frac{p}{2} + .368p + \frac{p}{2} + \frac{2}{\pi} + \frac{p}{2\pi} \frac{p-1}{3p-1} < \frac{2}{\pi} p \log p + .5p.$$

The same can be verified by computer computation for $p < 31$. Now, it is easy to see that the second expression in (6.1) is increasing with B , and so $|S_p(f, B)| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi} p \log p + .5p}$, for any $B \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$. If $B > p/2$, we can write $S_p(f(x), B) = S_p(f) - S_p(f(-x), p-B) = \chi_2(a)\mathcal{G}_p - S_p(f(-x), p-B)$ with $\mathcal{G}_p = \sqrt{p}$ or $\sqrt{p}i$, and apply the bound from the preceding sentence to the latter sum. \square

Example 6.1. A nontrivial bound of the sort $|S_p(f, B)| < B/2$ is not possible in general for B slightly smaller than \sqrt{p} , as the following example illustrates. For $B < p$ and B, p sufficiently large, we claim that

$$\left| \sum_{x=1}^B e_p(x^2) \right| > B \left(1 - \frac{4B^4}{p^2} \right). \quad (6.4)$$

Thus in order to have $|S_p(f, B)| < B/2$, we need $\frac{4B^4}{p^2} \geq \frac{1}{2}$, that is $B > \frac{1}{2^{3/4}} \sqrt{p}$. To establish (6.4), note that $\cos(2x) \geq 1 - 2x^2$, and so the real part of the sum is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{x=1}^B \cos(2\pi x^2/p) &\geq B - \frac{2\pi^2}{p^2} \sum_{x=1}^B x^4 = B - \frac{2\pi^2}{p^2} \frac{B(B+1)(2B+1)(3B^2+3B-1)}{30} \\ &\geq B - \frac{2\pi^2}{5} \frac{B^5}{p^2} \left(1 + O\left(\frac{1}{B}\right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Remark 6.1. One can also make use of van der Corput's Lemma, see, e.g., [18, pg. 18], to prove a result similar to Proposition 6.1. In this case, the analog of the sum over h in (6.3) can be restricted to an interval $1 \leq h \leq H$ with $H < B$, yielding a bound for $|S_p(f, B)|^2$ with dominant term $\frac{2p}{\pi} \frac{B+H}{H+1} \log(BH/p)$. Unfortunately, the slight increase in the factor in front of the logarithm (in comparison to $\frac{2p}{\pi}$) prevents any numeric improvement in our results.

7. Lemmas for the Divisor Function

To prove Theorems 1.3 and 1.4, we need the following results about the divisor function $\tau(n)$.

7.1. Upper Bound for $\tau(n)$

Nicolas and Robin [20] established the uniform upper bound

$$\tau(n) \leq n^{\frac{1.066018\dots}{\log \log n}},$$

for $n \geq 2$ with equality at $n = 6983776800 = 2^5 \cdot 3^3 \cdot 5^2 \cdot 7 \cdot 11 \cdot 13 \cdot 17 \cdot 19$.

7.2. Average Value of $\tau(n)$

Next, for any positive real x , write

$$\sum_{1 \leq n \leq x} \tau(n) = x \log x + (2\gamma - 1)x + \Delta(x).$$

Dirichlet established that $\Delta(x) = O(\sqrt{x})$ and many improvements in the order of magnitude of $\Delta(x)$ have been given since. It is widely believed that $\Delta(x) =$

$O_\varepsilon(x^{\frac{1}{4}+\varepsilon})$ with the fraction $1/4$ being best possible. Little work has been done on obtaining explicit upper bounds for $\Delta(x)$. The standard textbook proof of $\Delta(x) = O(\sqrt{x})$, gives with a little extra care, $|\Delta(x)| \leq \sqrt{x}$ for $x \geq 1$. This was improved to

$$|\Delta(x)| \leq .961\sqrt{x}, \quad (7.1)$$

for $x \geq 1$ by Berkane, Bordellès and Ramaré [1]. They also established the explicit estimate [1, Theorem 1.2],

$$\Delta(x) < .764 x^{1/3} \log x, \quad \text{for } x \geq 9995. \quad (7.2)$$

7.3. Average Value of $\tau(n)/n$

Finally, consider the sum $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\tau(n)}{n}$. The Laurent expansion

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\tau(n)}{n^s} = \zeta^2(s) = \frac{1}{(s-1)^2} + \frac{2\gamma}{s-1} + C + \dots,$$

with $C = \gamma^2 - 2\gamma_1 = .478809\dots$, where $\gamma = .577215\dots$ is Euler's constant and $\gamma_1 = -.0728158\dots$ is the first Stieltjes constant, gives the asymptotic $\sum_{n=1}^x \frac{\tau(n)}{n} \sim \frac{1}{2} \log^2 x + 2\gamma \log x + C$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$. This was made explicit in [1, Corollary 2.2]. In the next lemma, we correct and refine their result.

Lemma 7.1. *For real $x \geq 2$, we have*

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\tau(n)}{n} = \frac{1}{2} \log^2 x + 2\gamma \log x + C + O^*\left(\frac{2.1 \log x}{x^{2/3}}\right).$$

As noted earlier, the O^* means the constant in the big-oh can be taken to be 1. In [1], the constant C was stated as $\gamma^2 - \gamma_1$ and the big-oh term was $O^*\left(\frac{1.16}{x^{1/3}}\right)$.

Proof. Let x be a positive real number and c a constant such that for $t \geq x$, $\Delta(t) \leq ct^{1/3} \log t$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\tau(n)}{n} &= \sum_{n \leq x} \tau(n) \left(\frac{1}{x} + \int_n^x \frac{dt}{t^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{x} \sum_{n \leq x} \tau(n) + \int_1^2 \tau(1) \frac{dt}{t^2} + \int_2^3 (\tau(1) + \tau(2)) \frac{dt}{t^2} + \dots \\ &= \frac{1}{x} \int_1^x \tau(n) + \int_1^x \left(\sum_{n \leq t} \tau(n) \right) \frac{dt}{t^2} \\ &= \frac{1}{x} \sum_{n \leq x} \tau(n) + \int_1^x \frac{1}{t^2} \left(t \log t + (2\gamma - 1)t + \Delta(t) \right) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{x} \sum_{n \leq x} \tau(n) + \frac{1}{2} \log^2 x + (2\gamma - 1) \log x + \int_1^\infty \frac{\Delta(t)}{t^2} dt - \int_x^\infty \frac{\Delta(t)}{t^2} dt. \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\int_1^\infty \frac{\Delta(t)}{t^2} = \gamma^2 - 2\gamma - 2\gamma_1 + 1;$$

see, e.g., [12, (33)]. Using $|\Delta(x)| \leq cx^{1/3} \log x$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{x} \sum_{n \leq x} \tau(n) &= \frac{1}{x} \left(x \log x + (2\gamma - 1)x + O^*(cx^{1/3} \log x) \right) \\ &= \log x + 2\gamma - 1 + O^*\left(\frac{c \log x}{x^{2/3}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Again, using $|\Delta(t)| \leq ct^{1/3} \log t$ for $t \geq x$ and integrating by parts,

$$\left| \int_x^\infty \frac{\Delta(t)}{t^2} dt \right| \leq c \int_x^\infty \frac{\log t}{t^{5/3}} dt = \frac{3c \log x}{2x^{2/3}} + \frac{3c}{2} \int_x^\infty \frac{dt}{t^{5/3}} = \frac{3c \log x}{2x^{2/3}} + \frac{9c}{4x^{2/3}}.$$

Putting together the above, we get

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\tau(n)}{n} = \frac{1}{2} \log^2 x + 2\gamma \log x + \gamma^2 - 2\gamma_1 + O^*\left(\frac{5c \log x}{2x^{2/3}} + \frac{9c}{4x^{2/3}}\right).$$

By (7.2) we can take $c = .764$ for $x > 9995$, and thus the error term is bounded by $2.1 \log x / x^{2/3}$ for $x > 9995$. Computer computation shows that the same holds for $2 \leq x \leq 9995$. \square

8. Proof of Theorem 1.3

Let $C(x) = ax^3 + bx^2 + cx$. Following the method of Weyl as in (6.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} |S_p(f, B)|^2 &= B + 2\mathcal{R} \sum_{h=1}^{B-1} \sum_{x=1}^{B-h} e_p(f(x+h) - f(x)) \\ &\leq B + 2 \sum_{h=1}^{B-1} \left| \sum_{x=1}^{B-h} e_p(3ahx^2 + (3ah^2 + 2bh)x) \right| = B + 2C, \end{aligned} \quad (8.1)$$

say, with

$$C := \sum_{h=1}^{B-1} \left| \sum_{x=1}^{B-h} e_p(3ahx^2 + (3ah^2 + 2bh)x) \right|. \quad (8.2)$$

i) Suppose that $B < \sqrt{p/2}$ and put $\delta = \delta_p = \frac{1.0661}{\log \log p}$. We may assume that $B + 2C > 1.21B^{\frac{1}{2}}p^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{\delta}{2}} \log^{\frac{1}{2}} p$, else we are already done. Then

$$\frac{B}{2C} \leq \frac{B}{1.21B^{\frac{1}{2}}p^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{\delta}{2}} \log^{\frac{1}{2}} p - B} \leq \frac{1}{1.43p^{\frac{\delta}{2}}p^{\frac{1}{4}} \log^{\frac{1}{2}} p - 1} := \lambda_p,$$

and

$$|S_p(f, B)|^2 \leq B + 2C \leq 2\lambda_p C + 2C = 2(1 + \lambda_p)C.$$

Now, by Cauchy's inequality,

$$C^2 \leq (B-1) \sum_{h=1}^{B-1} \left| \sum_{x=1}^{B-h} e_p(3ahx^2 + (3ah^2 + 2bh)x) \right|^2.$$

Applying (6.3) to the quadratic sum over x gives

$$\begin{aligned} C^2 &\leq (B-1) \sum_{h=1}^{B-1} \left(B-h + 2 \sum_{j=1}^{B-h} \min \left\{ B-h, \frac{1}{|\sin(6ajh\pi/p)|} \right\} \right) \\ &\leq (B-1) \left(\frac{B(B-1)}{2} + 2 \sum_{h=1}^{B-1} \sum_{j=1}^{B-1} \min \left\{ B-1, \frac{1}{|\sin(6ajh\pi/p)|} \right\} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}B(B-1)^2 + 2(B-1) \sum_{1 \leq n < p} N(n) \min \left\{ B-1, \frac{1}{|\sin(6an\pi/p)|} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (8.3)$$

where

$$N(n) = \#\{(h, j) \in \mathbb{Z}^2 : hj \equiv n \pmod{p}, 1 \leq h, j \leq B-1\}. \quad (8.4)$$

Note that for $p/2 < n < p$, we have $N(n) = 0$ since $(B-1)^2 < p/2$, while for $n < p/2$, we have $N(n) < \tau(n) < p^{\frac{1.0661}{\log(\log p)}} = p^\delta$. Thus,

$$C^2 \leq \frac{1}{2}B(B-1)^2 + 2(B-1)p^\delta \sum_{n=1}^{(p-1)/2} \min \left\{ B-1, \frac{1}{|\sin(6an\pi/p)|} \right\}.$$

Now, as in the proof of Lemma 3.2, the sum over n is maximized when $6a \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, where it is bounded by

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{(p-1)/2} \min \left\{ B-1, \frac{1}{|\sin(n\pi/p)|} \right\} &\leq \sum_{n < p/(\pi B)} B + \sum_{p/(\pi B) < n < p/2} \frac{p}{\pi} \left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{2n}{p^2 - n^2} \right) \\ &< \frac{p}{\pi} + \frac{p}{\pi} \log \frac{\pi B}{2} + B + \frac{2p}{\pi(p^2 - (p/2)^2)} \sum_{1 \leq n \leq (p-1)/2} n \\ &= \frac{p}{\pi} \log B + \frac{p}{\pi} (1 + \log(\pi/2)) + B + \frac{p}{3\pi} \frac{p^2 - 1}{p^2} \\ &\leq \frac{p}{\pi} \log B + .5682p + B. \end{aligned} \quad (8.5)$$

Thus for $B < \sqrt{p/2}$,

$$\begin{aligned} C^2 &\leq \frac{1}{2}B(B-1)^2 + 2(B-1)p^\delta \left(\frac{p}{\pi} \log B + .5682p + B \right) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{4}pB + 2Bp^\delta \left(\frac{p}{2\pi} \log p + .4579p + B \right), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |S_p(f, B)|^4 &\leq 4(1 + \lambda_p)^2 \left(\frac{1}{4}pB + 2Bp^\delta \left(\frac{p}{2\pi} \log p + .4579p + B\right)\right) \\ &\leq (1.1)^4 Bp^{1+\delta} \log p, \end{aligned}$$

for $p > 10^9$. For $p < 10^9$ and $B < \sqrt{p/2}$, we trivially have $|S_p(f, B)|^4 \leq B^4 < (1.1)^4 Bp^{1+\delta} \log p$. Thus in all cases, if $B < \sqrt{p/2}$, then $|S_p(f, B)| \leq 1.1 (Bp)^{\frac{1}{4}} p^{\delta/4} \log^{\frac{1}{4}} p$.

ii) Suppose that $B > \sqrt{p/2}$. If $B > p^{2/3}$, then by (1.4),

$$|S_p(f, B)| < \Phi \log p \leq 2\sqrt{p} \log p < 1.38B^{\frac{3}{4}} p^{\delta/2} \log^{\frac{1}{4}} p.$$

Assume now that $B < p^{2/3}$. We have trivially

$$|S_p(f, B)| \leq B \leq 1.38 B^{\frac{3}{4}} p^{\frac{\delta}{2}} \log^{\frac{1}{4}} p,$$

for $B < (1.38)^4 p^{2\delta} \log p$. Since $B < p^{\frac{2}{3}}$, it suffices to have $p < 1.27 \cdot 10^{20}$.

Suppose now that $p > 1.27 \cdot 10^{20}$. Using the notation in (8.1), we may assume that $B + 2C > (1.38)^2 B^{\frac{3}{2}} p^\delta \log^{\frac{1}{2}} p$, and so

$$|S_p(f, B)|^2 \leq B + 2C \leq 2(1 + \lambda'_p)C,$$

with

$$\lambda'_p := \frac{1}{1.6 p^{\frac{1}{4} + \delta} \log^{\frac{1}{2}} p - 1}.$$

For any $n \leq p$ there are at most $\frac{B^2}{p} + 1$ integers m with $1 \leq m \leq B^2$ and $m \equiv n \pmod{p}$, and thus with $N(n)$ as defined in (8.4),

$$N(n) \leq \left(\frac{B^2}{p} + 1\right) \max_{m \leq B^2} \tau(m) \leq \left(\frac{B^2}{p} + 1\right) p^{2\delta}.$$

Thus from the analog of (8.3), allowing $n > p/2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} C^2 &\leq \frac{1}{2}B(B-1)^2 + 2(B-1) \sum_{1 \leq n < p} N(n) \min \left\{ B-1, \frac{1}{|\sin(6an\pi/p)|} \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2}B(B-1)^2 + 2(B-1) \left(\frac{B^2}{p} + 1\right) p^{2\delta} \sum_{1 \leq n < p} \min \left\{ B-1, \frac{1}{|\sin(6an\pi/p)|} \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2}B(B-1)^2 + 4(B-1) \left(\frac{B^2}{p} + 1\right) p^{2\delta} \sum_{1 \leq n < p/2} \min \left\{ B-1, \frac{1}{|\sin(n\pi/p)|} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

By (8.5), it follows that

$$C^2 \leq \frac{1}{2}B^3 + 4B \left(\frac{B^2}{p} + 1\right) p^{2\delta} \left(\frac{p}{\pi} \log B + .5682p + B\right),$$

and so for $p > 1.27 \cdot 10^{20}$, noting that $\lambda'_p < 10^{-10}$ and $B < p^{2/3}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |S_p(f, B)|^4 &\leq 4(1 + \lambda'_p)^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} B^3 + 4B \left(\frac{B^2}{p} + 1 \right) p^{2\delta} \left(\frac{p}{\pi} \log B + .5682 p + B \right) \right) \\ &\leq 4.0001 \left(\frac{4}{\pi} \frac{2}{3} p^{2\delta} B^3 \log p \left(1 + \frac{p}{B^2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{3\pi(.5682)}{2 \log p} + \frac{3\pi}{2p^{1/3} \log p} + \frac{3\pi}{16p^{2\delta} \log p (1+1/p^{1/3})} \right) \right) \\ &\leq (1.38)^4 B^3 \left(1 + \frac{p}{B^2} \right) p^{2\delta} \log p, \end{aligned}$$

as one can confirm by computation.

9. Proof of Theorem 1.4

Let $f(x) = x^3 + bx^2 + cx$ and suppose that $4p^{1/3} < B < \sqrt{p/12}$. In particular, $p > 7 \cdot 10^6$. Our goal is to show

$$|S_p(f, B)| < (Bp)^{1/4} \log^{1/4}(B^3/p) \log^{1/4}(Bp).$$

We have $|S_p(f, B)|^2 \leq B + 2C$ with C as given in (8.2), and so we are done if $B + 2C \leq (Bp)^{1/2}$. Suppose now that $2C > (Bp)^{1/2} - B$, implying

$$\frac{B}{2C} \leq \frac{1}{(p/B)^{1/2} - 1}.$$

From $B < \sqrt{p/12}$, we have $p/B > \sqrt{12p}$, and thus

$$\frac{B}{2C} \leq \beta_p := \frac{1}{(12p)^{1/4} - 1} < .0106.$$

Then $B + 2C \leq 2(1 + \beta_p)C$ and

$$|S_p(f, B)|^4 \leq (B + 2C)^2 \leq 4(1 + \beta_p)^2 C^2,$$

where by (8.3),

$$C^2 \leq \frac{1}{2} B(B-1)^2 + 2(B-1) \sum_{1 \leq n < p} N(n) \min \left\{ B-1, \frac{1}{|\sin(6n\pi/p)|} \right\}.$$

Noting that $N(n) = 0$ for $n > (B-1)^2$ and $N(n) \leq \tau(n)$ for $n \leq (B-1)^2$, the sum over n is at most

$$(B-1) \sum_{1 \leq n \leq \frac{p}{6B}} \tau(n) + \sum_{\frac{p}{6B} < n \leq B^2} \frac{\tau(n)}{|\sin(6n\pi/p)|} = \Sigma_1 + \Sigma_2$$

say. By (7.1),

$$\begin{aligned}\Sigma_1 &\leq (B-1) \left(\frac{p}{6B} \log \frac{p}{6B} + (2\gamma-1) \frac{p}{6B} + \sqrt{\frac{p}{6B}} \right) \\ &< \frac{p}{6} \log \frac{p}{6B} + \frac{p}{6} (2\gamma-1) + \sqrt{pB/6},\end{aligned}$$

and by Lemmas 3.1, 7.1, (7.2) and the fact that $\frac{6n}{p} < \frac{6B^2}{p} < \frac{1}{2}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}\Sigma_2 &\leq \sum_{\frac{p}{6B} < n \leq B^2} \frac{\tau(n)}{\pi} \left(\frac{p}{6n} + \frac{2(6n)/p}{1-(6n/p)^2} \right) \leq \sum_{\frac{p}{6B} < n \leq B^2} \frac{\tau(n)}{\pi} \left(\frac{p}{6n} + \frac{4}{3} \right) \\ &= \frac{p}{6\pi} \sum_{\frac{p}{6B} < n \leq B^2} \frac{\tau(n)}{n} + \frac{4}{3\pi} \sum_{\frac{p}{6B} < n \leq B^2} \tau(n) \\ &\leq \frac{p}{6\pi} \left(\frac{1}{2} \log^2 B^2 - \frac{1}{2} \log^2 \frac{p}{6B} + 2\gamma \log \frac{6B^3}{p} + \frac{4.2 \log(p/6B)}{(p/6B)^{2/3}} \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{4}{3\pi} \left(B^2 \log B^2 - \frac{p}{6B} \log \frac{p}{6B} + (2\gamma-1) \left(B^2 - \frac{p}{6B} \right) + 2B \right).\end{aligned}$$

The dominant term in $\Sigma_1 + \Sigma_2$ is

$$\frac{p}{12\pi} (\log^2 B^2 - \log^2 \frac{p}{6B}) = \frac{p}{12\pi} \log \frac{6B^3}{p} \log \frac{Bp}{6}.$$

By computer computation, we find that for $4p^{1/3} < B < \sqrt{p/12}$, we have

$$\frac{\Sigma_1 + \Sigma_2}{p \log(6B^3/p) \log(Bp/6)} < .0437.$$

Thus, for B in this range,

$$\begin{aligned}|S_p(f, B)|^4 &\leq 4(1 + \beta_p)^2 C^2 \leq 4(1.0106)^2 C^2 \\ &\leq 4.086 \left(\frac{1}{2} B(B-1)^2 + 2(B-1)(.0437)p \log(6B^3/p) \log(Bp/6) \right) \\ &\leq 4.086 \left(\frac{1}{24} Bp + (.0874)Bp \log(6B^3/p) \log(Bp/6) \right) \\ &< .358 Bp \log(6B^3/p) \log(Bp/6),\end{aligned}$$

yielding the desired bound.

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